

THE IMPORTANCE OF MASS MEDIA AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In this article mentioned about the importance of mass media and innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages. Millions of people are using the basic branches of media which are so popular, important and innovative at present day. Each type of mass media is based on its peculiar, special tasks that are very helpful for doing any kind of things in an intensive way. Actually, there are six branches of media, such as, broadcasting media, print media, internet media, digital media, indoor and outdoor media. Any types of media play a great role in doing activities.

First of all, the quality of the result of any activity depends directly on the student's personal interest. Watching movies and TV shows in the original will be a good motivation for learning the language and will help to diversify the monotonous and classes in grammar. Also, this is a unique opportunity to watch new movies, without waiting for a translation within a few months and become familiar with those materials that are not translated into Russian. This method develops the skill of perception of a foreign language by hearing. With daily exercises you can achieve good results in just a few months. At the same time, it helps to significantly expand lexical inventory. The context in which new words are used contributes to the understanding of the meaning as well as the lexical environment of each word. Movies and TV shows are examples of authentic speech (natural English and American), spoken by its speakers. It is necessary to learn what intonation should be spoken with, where to make logical pauses and stresses, and what pace of speech is preferable. As we come to some advantages and disadvantages of mass media, they can be up to how to use of it. The issue of media exposure to a large audience occupies a large number of states earlier than about a century. At the beginning of the 20th century, if numerous data transmission resources were fully formed, the concept of social community manipulation began to be plausible. With the emergence of the Internet, TV and broadcasting, society began the most informative. The information began in any way not only as a minority advantage, but as a home and important entry of a wide audience. In a similar way, the significance of this problem is indisputable, the connection has changed, which has the latest resources, and in accordance with this, the mission. Numerous communications, or in other texts, the media began as a translator of the

whole informative sphere of the community, and the resources of public data are important and one of the main social and political instruments of the country. In the field of social views, they act, as well as the principle, only these difficulties, data, actions, which are important, and in their own order stimulate social interest and allow ambiguous explanation, and also the likelihood of discussing the issue in the issues concerned. Thus, in the present world, an individual is subject to simultaneous influence from various places, similar to the media, as well as television broadcasting, print media, a magazine, and radio broadcasting. Public data resources are required to objectively and honestly translate thoughts and information in order to help the country and its residents to form a corresponding and absolute view of society and to be a platform for the purpose of direct conversation from within the community. And the preservation of the circumstances that allow the Internet, TV, broadcasting and printed media to be independent and independent in order to realize their own mission, must be a duty of a democratic country. There is a problem: in what way can the tools of public data make it possible to manifest such a tremendous impact in society and thereby create the most social judgment? First, it is necessary to single out the fact that today the public data resources directly provide a greater chance for people to get the freshest and most important announcements from each share of coverage, to find out about the situation in society. The channels of various states are presented with 1 and this fact is, according to different. Voting in the Crimea lit up without exception the most common Domestic news channels, like the same: "1st way", "Russia24", "Media Company", these channels emphasized the independence of selection and the absolute possibility of selection, outgoing to cast their vote. Autocephalous media: "Television Channel of Ukraine", "1st State", "Inter" reported about this, the fact that people have no authority to select, they are forced to cast their vote, and if they resist, they are threatened. Already after the annexation of the Crimea to the Russian Federation, earlier time passed, however the situation has not improved. Realizing that the assistance in the debate reduces his indicator categorically refused to role in the 5th round, recognizing, in a similar way, his own loss even up to the basis of the election. A clear advantage of Kennedy on the air soon in a significant way shook his Victoria in elections over Nixon, who up to the base of the televised debates was the favorite of the election race. In addition, the media have enormous and great abilities with the aim of rallying and bringing people together for a specific impact, or for extracting specific benefits. This particular family is a popularization, only more generally aimed at the interests of the most people, and not at all. Barack Obama is not able to boast such a degree of trust, only 45% of respondents sublimely evaluated his leadership qualities. In conclusion, the impact of media has got a great importance that is global in the world. With the help of media, people can do anything they like easily and comfortably, that is why, it is based on not only to get conveniences and opportunities, but also it develops human mind, knowledge and outlook.

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